

EDUCATION SYSTEM IN ECONOMICALLY DEVELOPED COUNTRIES**Abdualieva Asel**

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Abstract. *This study examines educational models in countries with developed educational systems based on scientific and theoretical pedagogical approaches. Our study provides information on the processes of using modern educational models in the application of educational methodologies in economically developed countries.*

Keywords: *Educational methods, pedagogical mechanisms, upbringing, educational mechanisms, pedagogical research, psychological approaches.*

IQTISODIY RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLARDA TA'LIM SISTEMASI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot ta'lim tizimi rivojlangan mamlakatlarda ilmiy va nazariy pedagogik yondashuvlarga asoslangan holda ta'lim modellarini o'rganadi. Tadqiqotimiz davomida iqtisodiy rivojlangan mamlakatlarning ta'lim metodikasini qo'llashda zamonaviy ta'lim modelini foydalanish jarayonlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ta'lim metodlari, pedagogik mexanizmlar, tarbiya, ta'lim mexanizmlari, pedagogik tadqiqotlar, psixologik yondashuvlar.*

Introduction

By studying the implementation of educational work in highly developed countries of the world and the implementation of it in schools, we will have additional rich resources to reorganize the national education systems of our independent republic, to quickly get rid of outdated and outdated forms and methods of activity in education and school work, and to adequately update them. After all, modern education should reflect the needs and interests of the state and society. It is advisable to study world experiences in the areas of scientific and technological progress and the development of society that can successfully function in the conditions of a new technological revolution, the introduction of a multi-variable third stage of secondary education, the use of the most advanced pedagogical tools in education, the creation of the most optimal systems for initiative and creativity in education, and the development of professional skills for the younger generation. This is of great importance for our education, which is currently undergoing large-scale reforms. In recent years, many articles and manuals on world education have been published,

seminars, conferences, readings, and meetings have been held on it. This is evidence of the rapid growth of attention and interest in the implementation of educational work in our education system and abroad. In developed countries, there are a large number of scientific institutions conducting pedagogical research. In Germany, there are more than 2 thousand of them. In France, the USA, and Japan, hundreds of state and private organizations, universities, and pedagogical research centers are engaged in the problems of educational theory. Their activities are coordinated by international educational centers, for example, the International Institute of Education in the USA. The activities of most of them are aimed at improving and restructuring the curriculum. The choice of the remaining subjects is at the discretion of students and parents. The pedagogical ideas of the "New World" also had a significant impact on education in France and Germany. In German secondary schools, along with the main subjects, elective curricula were implemented, which included chemistry, physics, and foreign languages. This curriculum is increasingly expanding beyond secondary schools and covering secondary schools and specialized ones. In French primary schools, the content of education is divided into basic subjects, including the mother tongue and literature, as well as psychology, and auxiliary subjects such as pedagogical education, labor education, and aesthetic education. In Japan, the curriculum has been significantly complicated, the set of basic subjects is much wider, and a number of new special and optional courses have been introduced. For example, the new music education curriculum of general education schools includes the study of national and world classical music. The reforms being carried out in schools have created problems of differentiation of educational work. In economically developed foreign countries, education is a social process that actively influences the internal policy of the country. For this reason, the amount of funds allocated for the economic provision of school needs in foreign countries is increasing from year to year. In Japan, for example, the idea that "a pedagogical school is not only a symbol of success and prosperity", but also "knowledge improves people" has become a belief and belief. Concern for education has always been the focus of attention of famous politicians. That is why it is not without reason that former US President R. Reagan, British Prime Minister M. Thatcher, and French President F. Mitterrand are called the initiators of school reform. F. Mitterrand considered the school to be "the driving force of society." In developed countries, there are numerous scientific institutions conducting pedagogical research. In Germany, there are more than 2 thousand of them. In France, the USA, and Japan, hundreds of state and private organizations, universities, and pedagogical research centers are engaged in the problems of educational theory. Their activities are coordinated by international educational centers, for example, the Institute of International

Education in the USA. The activities of most of them are aimed at improving and restructuring the curriculum. Since the 1980s, the range of subjects that must be studied has expanded in Great Britain, as in the USA. English and literature, mathematics, and natural sciences have become the core of the curriculum. The choice of the remaining subjects is up to the students and parents. The pedagogical ideas of the “New World” also have a significant impact on education in France and Germany. In German secondary schools, along with the main subjects, elective programs are also being implemented, which include chemistry, physics, and foreign languages. This curriculum is increasingly going beyond secondary schools and covering high schools and gymnasiums. Programs for working with gifted children are widespread in the United States. In some cities, high-class kindergartens have been opened, where 4-5-year-old students are taught according to the school program. In the United States, 600,000 of the most talented children are selected from high schools and colleges every year on the basis of the “Merit” program. Tests are conducted among them, and 35,000 of the most talented students are selected and trained. They are provided with various benefits, scholarships, good housing conditions, admission to the highest-ranking universities, and more. But the fate of mentally retarded students, who are at the opposite pole to gifted children, is also increasingly worrying foreign colleagues, a lot of preventive work is being carried out to study and prevent the causes of this situation, and special schools are being opened for them. However, statistics show that the number of such children is increasing. In the 70s, the implementation of the nationwide project of the School of the Future was launched in the USA. The content of this experiment is to work under the teacher's command, to give more students the opportunity to work independently. The educational content includes class work, independent study, and teacher consultation. In German schools, there is a trend towards reducing the number of students in the classroom. Individual packages (tasks) are distributed to each of such students. The student completes the tasks independently, and if necessary, he receives consultation from the teacher. The theoretical foundations of educational governance in Europe are based on well-established models such as bureaucratic, democratic, and participatory systems. These educational models affect various aspects of the educational process, including governance structures, pedagogical decision-making mechanisms and stakeholder participation. At the same time, European education systems are characterized by a strong focus on quality assurance, professional development and equitable resource allocation. This study examines the scientific and theoretical foundations that underpin educational governance in Europe. By examining different governance models, the role of decentralization and stakeholder involvement, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of how education is governed in different European contexts.

Through applied psychological research and comparative analysis, the study highlights key elements that contribute to the effectiveness and sustainability of European education systems and offers lessons that can be applied globally. The evolution of educational governance in Europe can be traced back to the Middle Ages, when education was largely controlled by religious institutions. Over time, the Enlightenment and the Industrial Revolution brought about significant changes in the way education was viewed and managed. Finland's education system is often considered one of the best in the world, with high levels of student achievement and psychological approaches. The country's decentralized model of educational governance emphasizes local autonomy, teacher professionalism, and minimal standardized testing. The role of local authorities in decision-making and strong community participation have helped create a system that is flexible, equitable, and responsive to local needs. France represents the opposite model, in which the Ministry of Education exercises significant control over the education system. The centralized nature of French education provides consistency across the country, but it has also been criticized for being rigid and slow to adapt to changing social needs. However, the centralised model allows for the consistent implementation of national education policies and reforms. Educational governance in Europe, with its diverse models and historical evolution, offers a wide range of insights into the effective management of education systems. Different theoretical frameworks, including bureaucratic, democratic and participatory models, have shaped the governance structures, decision-making processes and stakeholder engagement strategies used in European countries. These systems demonstrate that there is no single approach to educational governance, but rather a range of options that can be adapted to meet the specific needs of individual countries and regions. Centralised systems such as those in France emphasise the benefits of uniformity and consistency in educational policies, while decentralised systems such as those in Finland demonstrate the benefits of local autonomy, flexibility and community participation. Quality assurance, professional development for teachers and a focus on stakeholder participation are key components that have contributed to the success of European education systems. As Europe continues to address contemporary challenges such as digitalization, inclusion and sustainability, educational governance needs to be flexible and forward-thinking. Lessons learned from the European experience, such as decentralization, equity and active stakeholder participation, can serve as valuable guides for shaping the future of educational governance globally.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the model of educational management in developed countries provides a solid foundation for creating education systems that are sustainable, equitable, and responsive to

the needs of developing countries. The application of modern methods by applying the education systems of internationally economically developed countries is a more advanced stage of education.

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